

Time to Revamp the Slope Algorithm and KISS?

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6 *Abstract*—The slope and aspect algorithm, crucial for many
7 applications of digital elevation models suffers from a number of
8 variants that produce very similar results. While some early
9 implementations used other approaches, most current algorithms
10 use least squares to fit a surface to the analysis window, and then
11 derive two partial derivatives to estimate the slope and aspect.
12 Simplification of the least squares solution leads to the common
13 Evans methods. It is time to standardize on a single slope algorithm,
14 with four parameters that can be adjusted: the order of the
15 polynomial, the size of the window, whether the computation can
16 proceed with voids, and if it uses all available points in the window.
17 Pre-filtering of the DEM should not be needed with current DEMs,
18 but selection of a larger analysis window can smooth and generalize
19 the slope and aspect grids and have the same effect as pre-filtering.

I. INTRODUCTION

21 Slope is perhaps the most pervasive and important land surface
22 parameter (LSP) derived from digital elevation models (DEMs),
23 used in a multitude of applications. A true value for the slope at a
24 point does not exist; even when a geomorphologist measures slope
25 in the field, the value depends on the region over which the
26 measurement takes place. Aspect follows directly from slope;
27 more derived parameters like curvature require additional partial
28 derivatives.

29 The choices for slope computation involve several distinct
30 aspects:

- 31 1. The actual algorithm. The traditional and most common
32 terminologies use the originator’s name (e.g. Evans [1], Horn
33 [2], Zevenberger and Thorne [3], or Shary [4]), but some recent
34 descriptions refer to the mathematical basis, such as quadratic
35 [5] or least squares.
- 36 2. The window size used in the computations, most
37 commonly 3x3. The higher order partial derivatives for
38 curvature often require a larger window.
- 39 3. Use of all the points in the window, or only the required
40 points at the outer edge of the window. Typical
41 implementations use only 8 elevations, even when a window

42 larger than 3x3 has many more points. Third or higher order
43 polynomials require more than 8 points and must use all points
44 in a 5x5 window.

45 4. Allow the window to have missing data. This allows
46 computations at the edge of the DEM and over some data gaps,
47 with the drawback that the fitted surface could be an
48 extrapolation with perhaps unfortunate effects.

49 5. The need for pre-filtering of the DEM. This suggestion
50 [6, 7] dates to a time when overall DEM quality and resolution
51 differed greatly from current products derived from lidar or
52 later generation radar sensors.

53 The suggested computation uses least squares to fit a
54 polynomial trend surface to all points within the window [8]
55 centered on each pixel in the DEM, which introduces some
56 smoothing. The user can select the order of the polynomial, which
57 determines the terms in the equation and the minimum number of
58 points required (Table I). The quadratic equation below shows the
59 coefficients as components of the vector b returned by the least
60 squares solution, with higher order solutions merely adding more
61 terms to the equation. Previous authors have been inconsistent
62 about nomenclature for the coefficients, using different letters,
63 starting the sequence with the lowest or highest order terms, or
64 including the constants from the partial derivatives.

$$65 \quad z = b[1] + b[2]*x + b[3]*y + \\ 66 \quad \quad b[4]*x^2 + b[5]*x*y + b[6]*y^2 + \\ 67 \quad \quad b[7]*x^3 + b[8]*x^2*y + b[9]*x*y^2 + b[10]*y^3 + \\ 68 \quad \quad b[11]*x^4 + b[12]*x^3*y + b[13]*x^2*y^2 + \\ 69 \quad \quad b[14]*x*y^3 + b[15]*y^4$$

70 TABLE I. POLYNOMIAL ORDER REQUIREMENTS

Polynomial order	Terms in equation	Minimum window	Required elevations in window
1 (plane)	3	3x3	3 / 9
2	6	3x3	6 / 9
3	10	5x5	10 / 25
4	15	5x5	15 / 25

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72 Slope and aspect require first order partial derivative z_x and z_y ,
73 Curvature requires three second order partial derivatives, z_{xx} , z_{xy} ,
74 and z_{yy} .

75 The central point has coordinates (0,0), with surrounding
76 points in terms of DEM grid spacings dx and dy in meters, which
77 can be efficiently computed even for DEMs with arc second
78 spacing [9]. When evaluating the partial derivatives at the central
79 point, all terms with x or y disappear. For slope or aspect, the first
80 or second order polynomials have the same $b[2]$ and $b[3]$
81 coefficients and produce the same results as the Evans [1] or Shary
82 methods [4]. The third and fourth order polynomials produce
83 identical slope and aspect values, which differ from the lower
84 order polynomials because their $b[2]$ and $b[3]$ differ.

85 All slopes in this paper are reported in percent, and the aspects
86 are in degrees with respect to true north.

87 II. DATA USED

88 We merged 4 USGS DTMs at 1 m UTM grid spacing, each
89 10km x 10 km, covering part of Glacier National Park in Montana.
90 We created a 30 m DEM by mean aggregation, and then extracted
91 a 500 x 500 subset (the largest we can display for the figures in
92 this paper). We also created a 500 x 500 subset of the 1 m DEM,
93 which covers a tiny fraction (1/900th) of the 30 m DEM.

105

94 **1 m UTM DTM** **30 m UTM DTM**
95 Figure 1. Montana test areas. Outline of 1 m DTM shown on the 30 m DTM.

96 III. RESULTS

97 Figures 2 and 3 shows the effect of changing the window size
98 for the order 1 or 2 polynomial, using all points in the window for
99 the least squares solution. Increasing the window size smooths the
100 resulting grids, but neither of these DTMs has appreciable noise
101 and smoothing would only be needed if the user wanted
102 generalization to remove some fine detail. Figure 4 shows that for
103 both these DTMs, the parametric isotropic filtering recommended
104 [6,7] has negligible effect on the slope grids.

106 **3x3 window** **5x5 window** **7x7 window** **9x9 window**
107 Figure 2. Effect of changing the computation window for the order 1 or 2 polynomial for the 30 m DTM, for slope (top row) and aspect (bottom row).

108 window 3x3 window 9x9
 109 Figure 3. Effect of changing computation window for order 1 or 2 polynomial
 110 for the 1 m DTM, for slope (top row) and aspect (bottom row).

111
 112 Figure 4. Negligible effects of parametric isotropic filtering before slope
 113 computation on the 1 m and 30 m DTMs. The r^2 value is shown in the upper left
 114 corner of the graphs.

115 While a higher order polynomial is required for the higher
 116 order partial derivatives needed to compute curvature, it makes
 117 little difference for slope computations. Figure 5 compares the
 118 slopes from the first/second order polynomial with the third/fourth
 119 order polynomial. In simple surfaces all of the polynomials will
 120 be equally good and most differences are very small. Moderate
 121 differences only occur at the breaks in steep slopes on the cliff
 122 edges and canyon bottoms.

123 Figure 6 shows a correlation matrix for the 4 most common
 124 traditional slope algorithms, and the two least squares polynomials

125 with different window sizes. The figure on the right shows the
 126 mean absolute differences; by taking the absolute values, high and
 127 low differences cannot cancel out. The least squares polynomial
 128 with a 3x3 window correlates extremely highly with the traditional
 129 algorithms, and has very small mean absolute differences.

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132 Figure 5. Difference between slope maps for the 30 m DTM computed with an
 133 order 1 or 2 polynomial and an order 3 or 4 polynomial. Red colors for the
 134 lower order polynomial yielding steeper slopes, and blue when the higher order
 135 polynomial is steeper.

136 IV. CONCLUSIONS

137 **Prefiltering the DEM before slope computations:** with
 138 current DEMs there may be no need for this (Figure 4). If the
 139 analysis would benefit from smoothing and generalization beyond
 140 that introduced by the polynomial, use of a larger computation
 141 window could achieve the same result without creation of a filtered
 142 DEM (Figures 2 and 3). The story might be different with integer
 143 resolution DEMs, but those have passed their expiration date and
 144 should be retired. High resolution lidar DEMs might benefit from
 145 smoothing, or alternatively aggregation to a coarser resolution
 146 which better matches the scale of interest.

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Figure 6. Correlation (left) and mean absolute differences (right) among slope algorithms for a 30 m DEM.

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151 **Use of a higher order polynomial:** for slope and aspect, order
152 3 or 4 polynomials (which produce identical results) have results
153 that are substantially different from the traditional estimates of
154 slope and should not be used for slope and aspect. Future work
155 might attempt to determine what the “true” slope should be.

156 **Window size:** all points in the 3x3 window should be used,
157 and only computed when the window contains no missing data
158 [10]. Larger windows should be used only when generalization
159 and smoothing are required.

160 Choosing the best algorithm for curvature is beyond the scope
161 of this paper. Curvatures are among the LSPs with the greatest
162 variability when comparing the current one arc second global
163 DEMs to reference data [11], and geomorphometry programs
164 show much bigger differences in their computations for curvature
165 compared to slope or aspect. If the requirements for the higher
166 order partial derivatives to compute curvature require a more
167 complex estimate for the local terrain surface, perhaps the
168 computation for slope should use a simpler formulation, and users
169 of curvature should understand their metrics could have significant
170 uncertainties.

171 V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

172 The suggested algorithm is implemented in MICRODEM [12,
173 13], with options to rapidly compare the effect of varying
174 parameters. While MICRODEM is primarily a GUI program, it
175 can be invoked from the command line to create slope and aspect
176 maps using the methodology described in this paper.
177 MICRODEM created all the figures in this paper. A preprint [10]
178 contains additional figures and analysis.

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